

Metacognitive Illusions Induced by Retrieval of Episodically Related Information

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Judgments of learning

- Judgment of learning: How well is material encoded?
 - Can be made during the learning event
 - Immediate judgments of learning—*immediate JOLs*
 - e.g., as you study for a test
 - Or after learning
 - Delayed judgments of learning—*delayed JOLs*
 - e.g., delayed testing before actual test

Typical laboratory designs

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Metamemory Theories

- Cue utilization theory
 - Metacognitive judgments are inferential in nature
 - Judgments are based on three types of metacognitive cues
 - Intrinsic
 - Extrinsic
 - Mnemonic

Metamemory Theories

- Cue utilization theory
 - Metacognitive cues arise from experience or beliefs

Cue Utilization Theory

- Encoding fluency
 - Contributes to immediate JOLs
- Processing fluency
 - Contributes to immediate and delayed cue-target JOLs
- Retrieval fluency
 - Contributes to delayed cue-only JOLs (delayed JOL effect)
- Encoding/Processing fluency \neq good indicator of future memorability
- Retrieval fluency $=$ good indicator of future memorability

Current Research Questions

- Is retrieval fluency only a good indicator for the memorability of the to-be-retrieved information itself?
- Can the retrieval attempt inform learners about the memorability of other information?
 - Retrieving previously encountered information could allow participants to experience retrieval fluency when making immediate JOLs for new items
 - “Educating subjective experience” (Koriat & Bjork, 2006)

Current Research Goal

- Manipulate conditions that allow or prevent retrieval of previously encountered information
 - Does retrieving previously encountered information impact current JOLs?

Exp 1: Design

Key		Reference Presentation
Reference: Cue – Only	Reference: Cue - Target	□ : Cue - Only
Transfer: Cue – Only	Transfer: Cue - Only	□ : Cue - Target

Study Block 1a

Study Block 1b

Exp 1 Results: JOL Distributions

Exp 1 Results: Gamma between JOLs and Final Recall

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Exp 1: Effect of Reference Item Recall on Transfer Item JOLs

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Exp 1 Results: Effect of Reference Item JOLs on Transfer Item JOLs

Exp 1 Results: Effect of Reference Item JOLs on Transfer Item JOLs

Experiment 1: Summary

- Experiencing different degrees of retrieval fluency for previously encountered information does not improve item level metacognitive accuracy
- Instead, retrievability of the previous information inflates metacognitive judgments for transfer items

Experiment 2

- Some evidence from Experiment 1 led us to wonder whether participants might be using the immediate JOLs for transfer items to guide the making of delayed JOLs for reference items rather than vice versa
 - Only a weakly bimodal distribution of JOLs for reference items made with delayed cue-only JOLs
 - Similar positive associations between reference and transfer item JOLs for delayed cue-only and delayed cue-target JOLs
- In Experiment 2, we elicited JOLs at different times for reference and transfer items

Exp 2: Design

Exp 2 Results: JOL Distributions

Exp 2 Results: Effect of Reference item Recall on Transfer Item JOLs

Exp 2 Results: Effect of Reference item JOLs on Transfer Item JOLs

Experiment 2: Summary

- Like Experiment 1, successful retrieval of previously encountered information inflates metacognitive judgments
 - Separating the timing of reference and transfer item JOLs clarified strong association between the JOLs when based on retrieval
- Experiencing retrieval fluency of previously encountered information does not improve metacognitive resolution

Conclusions

- Evidence for a metacognitive illusion
 - Successful retrieval of previously encountered information can lead learner to overestimate retrievability of new information
 - Perhaps might have predicted an effect of this sort, but could have predicted it in opposite direction
 - Transfer items might seem weaker than a retrieved reference item, stronger than an unretrieved reference item
- Methodological point
 - Mixing delayed and immediate JOLs can have an adverse impact on resolution for immediate JOLs
 - Possible contribution to size of delayed-JOL effect when using such a method